

Evaluation of pyroquilon seed treatment for blast (BI) control in upland rice

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We tested the effectiveness of pyroquilon (CGA49104), a systemic seed dressing fungicide, for BI control. A field trial in a randomized complete block design with three replications was laid out in cerrado soil in Goiânia. Six plots each 5 m long with 50 cm spacing were seeded on 6 Nov 1983. Seeds of rice IAC25, IAC164, L 50, IAC47, CNA104, and B-34-2 were treated with different doses of pyroquilon and benomyl slurry. Untreated checks were maintained.

Heavy BI incidence was obtained by planting four closely spaced spreader rows of susceptible rice varieties around each block. Lesions/leaf and percent leaf area affected, were recorded 29, 34, 38, 42, 46, and 50 d after seeding (DS). Percent panicle BI was also recorded.

At 29 DS pyroquilon significantly reduced BI infection in all varieties as compared to the benomyl-treated and the untreated control (see table). Varieties did not significantly differ in panicle BI or yield but were significantly different in susceptibility to leaf BI. At 38 DS, pyroquilon treatment reduced leaf BI from 28 to <5% in susceptible IAC47 and IAC25. Treatment of moderately resistant

Effect of pyroquilon seed treatment on leaf BI in 6 upland rice varieties, Goiania, Brazil.

Treatment ^a	Sporulating lesions (no./leaf) 29 DS	Leaf area affected ^b (%)			
		34 DS	38 DS	42 DS	46 DS
Medium-duration varieties					
IAC47					
Pyroquilon	0.05 a	3 a	4 a	24 a	39 a
Benomyl	1.17 b	23 b	28 b	42 a	44 a
Untreated control	1.42 b	22 b	29 b	39 a	41 a
CNA104-B-4-1-1					
Pyroquilon	1.03 a	1 a	1 a	2 a	5 a
Benomyl	1.33 b	4 a	3 a	7 a	7 a
Untreated control	1.08 b	4 a	4 a	7 a	13 a
CNA104-B-34-2					
Pyroquilon	0 a	0 a	0 a	1 a	2 a
Benomyl	0.21 b	2 a	1 a	2 a	4 a
Untreated control	0.31 b	1 a	2 a	4 a	6 a
Short-duration varieties					
IAC25					
Pyroquilon	0.03 a	0 a	2 a	16 a	26 a
Benomyl	1.60 b	20 b	28 b	34 b	34 a
Untreated control	1.50 b	16 b	23 b	30 b	38 a
IAC164					
Pyroquilon	0.05 a	1 a	3 a	15 a	24 a
Benomyl	0.84 ab	10 ab	14 ab	14 a	17 a
Untreated control	1.20 b	16 b	17 b	24 a	32 a
L 50					
Pyroquilon	0.04 a	0 a	1 a	11 a	23 a
Benomyl	0.63 b	8 ab	13 a	13 a	26 a
Untreated control	0.52 b	12 b	15 a	16 a	18 a

^aDosage = pyroquilon 400 g ai/100 kg seed, benomyl 400 g ai/100 kg seed. ^bIn a column treatment means by variety followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

CNA104-B-34-2 kept disease level at 5% until 50 DS although differences were significant only at 29 DS.

We also tested pyroquilon in a BI nursery experiment. Seeds of IAC25, IRAT112, IAC47, and CNA104-B-34-2 were treated with carbofuran, pyroquilon, or pyroquilon + carbofuran. An untreated control was maintained. Leaf BI severity

and dry matter production were recorded. Differences between the chemical treatments, varieties, and interactions were significant. The correlation between biomass and leaf BI was negative and highly significant ($r = -0.91^{**}$).

Seed treatment with carbofuran did not affect the efficiency of pyroquilon treatment for BI. □

Races of the rice bacterial blight (BB) pathogen in the Philippines from 1980 to 1982

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In 1980-82, leaves naturally infected with 209 BB isolates were randomly collected from native, local, traditional, and IR lines or varieties. The rices, usually with the *Xa 4* gene for resistance, came from various Philippine sites. The pathogen was isolated in the laboratory.

To determine BB race frequency, the isolates were tested for their reaction on IR8, IR20, IR1545-339, CAS 209, and

DV85, each of which has different genes for BB resistance. In the greenhouse, 40-d-old plants of each variety were arranged in rows and inoculated with each isolate by clipping the 2 youngest, fully expanded leaves of each tiller. Disease level based on lesion length was recorded 14 d after inoculation and converted to percentage leaf area infected as described in the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Most isolates collected since 1980 belonged to race 2, followed by race 3, both of which are virulent to rices with the *Xa 4* gene for resistance. Such rices include IR20, IR36, and all IRRI released varieties (Table 1). Race 1, the predominant race before wide cultivation of

Table 1. Race frequency of the field population of *X. campestris* in the Philippines with specific virulence to a set of differential varieties, IRRI.

Race	Reaction to differential varieties ^a	Frequency ^b (%)		
		1980	1981	1982
1	SRRSR	1.9	0	0.8
2	SSRRR	75.9	87.5	85.4
3	SSRSR	14.8	3.1	9.8
4	SRSSR	0	3.1	0.8
5	SRRRR	0	6.3	1.6
6	SSSSMS	7.4	0	1.6

^aDifferential varieties corresponding to the reaction pattern of each race: IR8, IR20, IR1545-339, Cas 209, DV85. ^bNumber of isolates tested each year: 1980 = 54, 1981 = 32, 1982 = 123.

BB-resistant varieties, had markedly decreased frequency (Table 1). Previously